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Towards Professionally-Oriented Reading Proficiency: ESP Curriculum Design

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Rezumat: Adaptarea curriculumului disciplinei „Limba engleză – limbaj specializat” (LELS) la nevoile socioeconomice actuale este indispensabilă în ceea ce privește dobândirea de către studenți a competențelor lingvistice necesare unei activități eficiente, atât în mediul academic, cât și în cel profesional. În societatea cunoașterii, competența de lectură

în limba străină este o abilitate esențială pentru accesul direct la informații de specialitate autentice. Implicit, lectura constituie premisa dezvoltării unor competențe temeinice de comunicare în limba străină. Articolul își propune să detalieze cadrul, avantajele și provocările proiectării curriculumului LELS, al cărui obiectiv didactic este de a optimiza învățarea limbii engleze de către studenții-ingineri prin exploatarea eficientă a textelor de specialitate.

Cuvinte-cheie: proiectarea curriculumului, competența de lectură, text de specialitate, aliniere constructivă.

Abstract: Adapting the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) curriculum to the current socio-economic needs is imperative in terms of endowing undergraduates with the necessary skills to function efficiently in both academic and professional settings. In the era of knowledge and specialization, reading competence has proven to be an essential skill for the acquisition of authentic specialized input; implicitly, it constitutes the premise for a sound communication competence development. The article aims to discuss the framework, challenges, and affordances of designing the ESP curriculum, the teaching objective of which is to foster engineering students' English language learning by means of efficient specialized text exploration.

Keywords: curriculum design, literacy skills, specialized text, constructive alignment.

INTRODUCTION

Current realities, determined by fulminant technological development and globalization, have generated new challenges and opportunities not just for the professional community, but for the educational sphere as well. In

order to respond efficiently to engineering job requirements, new models for teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP) ought to be developed, which will endow students with the necessary skills to become proficient users of specialized discourse. Taken that the purpose of ESP learning is “situated language use” [2, p. 8] and that ESP teaching is aimed at “developing procedures appropriate to learners whose main purpose is learning English for a purpose other than just learning the language system” [6, p. 3], content-area learning and language learning need to be mutually supportive in engineering education. In this context, the question is what approach should be adopted in designing a modern language course to help students master the specialized discourse and equip them with the relevant linguistic and life skills for their future careers?

Literacy researchers [10, p. 11; 11, p. 86; 14, p. 89] maintain that in higher education settings reading has been recognized as the primary, underlying skill for the acquisition of meaningful content-area and specialized knowledge. On the one side, reading is indispensable in receiving, integrating and assimilating specialized knowledge, synthesized from multiple written sources. On the other side, it yields essential vocabulary, linguistic, and text conventions needed for deepening the students’ language proficiency. Moreover, reading is seen as “a stepping stone to other skills development or as complementing them” [11, p. 86]. Academically and professionally-oriented reading in English has been an ever-expanding need, since students engaged in content-area knowledge acquisition have instant access to an overwhelming flow of information. It compels today’s students to be fast and rather selective in the content available, while being able to evaluate critically the usefulness of that information for their personal and professional lives. Yet in university settings, where reading competence is taken for granted, not too much is done to increase students’ awareness of efficient reading techniques and strategies [10, p. 89].

In light of the above, we aim to tackle the challenges and affordances of developing a specialized foreign language curriculum in general, and to propose a framework of ESP curriculum design aimed at fostering specialized language teaching and learning by means of reading competence development in particular. The curriculum was conceived and implemented within a pedagogical experiment conducted at the Technical University of Moldova (TUM) in 2018-2019, involving 90 second-year civil engineering and architecture students.

BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE OVERVIEW

The process of conceptualizing and designing a university curriculum/syllabus is both an essential enterprise and a real endeavor for academic staff. Consequently,

curriculum design research is a central preoccupation for many ESL/ESP researchers, practitioners, and policy-makers [3,4,5,6,12,15,16]. It is important to point out that the terms *curriculum* and *syllabus* are often used interchangeably. Although both of them outline a plan of what is to be achieved through teaching and learning, there are differences between the two. A curriculum is three-dimensional, as it takes into account student needs, subject content, and teaching methodology, while a syllabus is a unidimensional document, which merely presents the content of the subject matter to be studied, and is actually based on a curriculum. Designing and implementing an ESP course was described by Dudley-Evans & St John [7] as a set of overlapping, interdependent phases: 1) needs analysis; 2) course (syllabus) design; 3) materials selection and production; 4) teaching and learning; 5) evaluation.

NEEDS ANALYSIS

Generally, an ESP course is tailored for a specific group of students with specific academic or professional needs. Dudley-Evans considers needs analysis to be the key defining feature of ESP [8, p. 133]. Needs analysis pertains to “the activities involved in gathering information that will serve as the basis for developing a curriculum that will meet the learning needs of a particular group of students” [5, p. 35]. Course designers commonly analyze student needs according to students’ background knowledge and skills, learning conditions, motivation for learning ESP etc. In their often-cited learning-centered approach to ESP, Hutchinson & Waters suggested to embrace a learning needs approach as the best route to guide learners from the starting point to the target situation [12, p. 54]. The authors maintain that learner needs are approached from two directions: (1) target needs (necessities, lacks and wants) – “what the learner needs to do in the target situation” – and (2) learning needs, referring to numerous factors, including the learners’ socio-cultural background, learning background, age, gender, knowledge of specialized contents, attitudes towards English learning etc. [12, pp. 54-56]. The success of bridging the gap between the target group’s needs and the expected learning outcomes depends on the capacity of the foreign language teacher to accurately identify learners’ needs and to align the teaching goals, course content, and appropriate ESP methodology towards attaining the intended outcomes.

By all means, in a student-centered course goals must arise directly from students’ needs, interests, and abilities. Such information is gathered from questionnaires, interviews, and teachers’ observations. Still, assuming that undergraduates are not fully aware of future L2 challenges in academic and professional settings, Aebersold & Field argue that besides student-contributed needs,

due attention should be given to teacher-perceived needs as well [1, p. 35]. In the opinion of Basturkmen, ESP teachers are more likely to focus on conceptual needs/disciplinary content, as well as language needs, than most undergraduates do, the reason behind this assertion being that pre-experienced students haven't developed a conceptual (disciplinary) base yet [2, p. 139].

CURRICULUM/SYLLABUS DESIGN

According to Clark and Mayer (2002), cited by Stefani [16, p. 54], "the term *design* encompasses the entire process of analyzing learning needs and goals and the development of a delivery system to meet those needs". In practical terms, it entails the use of theoretical and empirical data to produce a syllabus [12, p. 65], to decide on an approach to adopt and the teaching materials to select that best suit to reach those goals [1, p. 35].

The principle of 'constructive alignment' is central to curriculum design and development in higher education, where 'constructive' emerges from the constructivist theory – learners use their own schemata to construct knowledge, and 'alignment' is a principle in curriculum theory, based on which assessment tasks should be aligned to what is intended to be learned [3, p. 97]. Biggs & Tang point out that in a constructively aligned system, "all components – intended learning outcomes, teaching/learning activities, assessment tasks and their grading – support each other, so the learner is enveloped within a supportive learning system" [3, p. 106]. In an ESP reading-focused curriculum, constructive alignment pertains to ensuring that the learning outcomes, derived from target learners' needs, are clear, effective, and achievable for all stakeholders, and that teaching-learning-assessment activities lead to the reading proficiency level relevant to students' target career. Thus, Breen details a number of key features/elements any syllabus ideally should provide: a clear framework of knowledge and capabilities appropriate to overall aims; continuity in classroom work for the teacher and the students; a basis for evaluating students' progress; a basis for evaluating the appropriateness of the course in relation to overall aims and student needs; content appropriate to the broader language curriculum, the particular educational and social situation [4, p. 151].

Whether starting from scratch or redesigning the existing curriculum, a number of key steps to effective course and curriculum design need to be followed: (1) consider your general aims for the course; (2) write specific learning outcomes (objectives); (3) plan the assessment framework to match your objectives; (4) plan the content, i.e. sequence of topics/readings; (5) plan the teaching/learning design; (6) compile a list of resources; (7) write the course outline, including readings; (8) consider evaluation of the course (formative and

summative) and how evaluation can be carried out best [16, p. 50]. Furthermore, an ESP curriculum requires continuous improvement even though it follows all the above-mentioned key features and design steps. In-class teacher's observations often reveal valuable ideas/directions/insides, which may involve making adjustments through the course to ensure that the set learning outcomes or the proficiency level will be achieved at the end of the course.

MATERIALS SELECTION

In ESP curriculum design, an essential component of the "delivery system" [16, p. 54] implies the development and evaluation of teaching and learning materials/activities. Unfortunately, commercial ESP textbooks, imported curricula, programs, and activities are often inappropriate to local context due to a high discrepancy in the linguistic proficiency of students within the same group. Furthermore, students' narrow specialization, high book prices, and a barely sufficient number of teaching hours are a hindrance in selecting the relevant book(s). Therefore, the teacher's solution at hand is to customize by any means the course materials, based on student needs and institutional constraints. Features of relevant future professional discourse, as well as text authenticity and innovativeness determine ESP material selection. Therefore, such lexical peculiarities of technical discourse as monoreferentiality, precision, transparency of terms, conciseness, redundancy, and lexical productivity [9, pp. 25-39] are strictly observed in the selection of course texts. The four precepts for the development of ESP materials ought to be equally observed: 1) to be relevant to the needs of students; 2) to correspond to their competence levels; 3) to involve creative tasks/activities; 4) to stimulate speech activity in the target language.

TEACHING AND LEARNING

Both teaching and learning play a pivotal role in the educational process, in which the full commitment of all participants is essential for the achievement of pertinent outcomes: the teacher's expertise, time, and meticulous planning need to be sustained by the learners' conscious involvement in the acquisition and consolidation of reading skills, both in class and in autonomous work.

In essence, reading is an active, fluent activity, which involves the reader getting meaningfully engaged with a text in a specific context. In academic and professional settings, some aspects of reading are crucial for appropriate specialized discourse acquisition. However, such issues as summarizing, synthesizing information, making inferences, critically responding to technical text input, as well as many others represent a great challenge for foreign language students. Correspondingly, thorough reading strategy instruction and substantial practice is in-

dispensable. On the assumption that developing of one's academic literacy and content-area knowledge frequently involves the integration of both receptive and productive skills, an integrated-skill approach to ESP teaching seems legitimate in this context: "the receptive skills function as necessary inputs to the productive skills, with each receptive skill having its place with each productive skill" [13, p. 6]. Moreover, the integration of language skills occurs naturally in academic contexts: the connections between reading, writing, listening, and speaking are inevitable in the teaching-learning process.

EVALUATION

Evaluation, a constitutive element of curriculum design, serves as "a quality assurance measure" for both student learning assessment and the efficacy of the teaching act [16, p. 56]. The process of collecting and interpreting learners' assessment data provides a clear picture of the effect of teaching on students' learning. Thus, besides providing data regarding the course's effectiveness in developing the targeted competencies, evaluation offers clues concerning the improvement of contents, approaches, methods etc. Evaluation can convey valuable data "on student attainment (summative evaluation), student approaches to and understanding of the learning context and indicate the knowledge gaps on which to make future decisions (formative evaluation), and supports the iterative process of curriculum design, development and delivery", asserts Stefani [16]. As such, according to clear-cut competence descriptors encompassed in the curriculum, students' performance is monitored and assessed within the initial, formative, and summative evaluations, followed by teacher's feedback and guidance on further linguistic competence scaffolding.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In our endeavor to optimize the ESP teaching-learning process, we focused on enhancing the engineering students' professionally-oriented reading skills as an impetus to developing much-needed English communication skills and further learning in academic and professional settings. In the experimental study conducted at TUM, there were involved 90 second-year students from two faculties: Urbanism, Architecture, & Construction and Geodesy & Cadaster. The purpose of the research project was to develop an instructional model aimed at facilitating ESP acquisition through the improvement of specialized text reading. In order to conceive and design the English course curriculum, we had to: first, determine the aspects of reading that are crucial for the academic and professional needs of students and set the learning objectives; second, to select pertinent materials to increase the students' motivation for reading English specialized texts; third, to adjust the

teaching methods to the expected learning outcomes; and finally, to formulate reading competence descriptors and assess the students' progress. First of all, we developed an exhaustive questionnaire (self-assessment of reading skills; difficulties encountered in specialized text reading and ways for managing them; students' perception of the role of reading strategies in gaining specialized language skills; specific reading strategies used) aimed at identifying the needs of engineering students regarding their reading skills development. Thus, the first step in the design of the new curriculum was to convert the quantitative data collected from students' questionnaire into course/learning objectives. Following the definition of reading competence according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFL), as well as Grab & Stoller's [10, pp. 9-10] observations regarding the essential components of reading skills, we established the key objectives (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) of the course.

As mentioned above, aligning the teaching goals, course content, and appropriate ESP methodology is paramount for reaching the expected learning outcomes. On the whole, we agree with the viewpoint of Biggs and Tang [3, p. 106] that the teacher's focus should rather be on how the content is learned, to what standard, not on the topic itself. Nevertheless, we consider that the discussed topics are capable of being either motivating or demotivating factors in language skills improvement. The rethought curriculum aimed at changing the students' perspective towards the importance of solid reading skills in specialized discourse acquisition. For that purpose, the studied topics were made more appealing (Sustainable Development, The Lost Art of Architectural Design, How Structures Fail, Improving Today's Concrete Technology etc.), supported by thought-provoking specialized texts, which not merely served as sources of specialized terminology and text conventions written by domain experts, but also stimulated the practicing of speaking, writing, and listening. For the most part, a skillful maneuvering of texts/topics that are close to students' real-life expectations and interests has a "dangling carrot" effect on engineers-to-be – their motivation for linguistic skills development is consequently boosted. Accordingly, the students' drive to gain deeper and more meaningful engagement with target community texts provides a favorable pedagogical context for achieving the course goals.

Moreover, it was important to identify appropriate comprehension strategies that would enable the students to extract the communicative value from technical texts while helping struggling learners overcome reading difficulties at the same time. For instance, within the Technological Model (TM), implemented over one semester,

an efficient use of reading comprehension strategies and techniques was taught; cooperative learning (pair, group, class discussion) was encouraged; the applicability of relevant internet resources (dictionaries, video recordings, specialized websites etc.) was demonstrated; the transfer of skills beyond the classroom was emphasized.

The students' reading skills were assessed according to CEFL competence descriptors, adapted for ESP needs, i.e. quizzes/portfolio/projects/tests/exams measured the students' linguistic proficiency relevant to their target career.

We are fully aware of the limitations of the implemented TM. First, it is unreasonable to reduce the reading competence development to one-semester instruction; it ought to be extended over both the General English course (first university year) and the content-area instruction. Another possible limitation of the study could be related to the fairly small number of participants (90). Finally, for the achievement of pertinent outcomes, full commitment of all the participants in the teaching-learning process is essential.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current study was derived from the research-based TM implemented at TUM in the 2018-2019 academic year. In this article we have tackled the challenges and affordances of tailoring an ESP curriculum, which prioritized reading competence development as a prerequisite of basic linguistic skills enhancement. Since it is not an engineering subject, all stakeholders tend to perceive the ESP course with a certain degree of reluctance. Still, clear learning outcomes, based on students' needs analysis, institutional constraints, and limitations, ought to be formulated by the curriculum developer.

Guided by the principle of constructive alignment in curriculum design, teaching-learning-evaluation activities should be aligned to the intended learning outcomes: meticulously selected teaching methods and materials should favor developing both receptive and productive skills; students' knowledge and interests in engineering topics need to be capitalized upon in order to boost their motivation for further reading while simultaneously extending their reading strategy repertoire; encountered linguistic difficulties have to be dealt with during the three reading phases, feedback sessions, and tutorials; students' progress has to be assessed according to the clear-cut competence descriptors enclosed in the curriculum.

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